

SAYINGS AS A SOURCE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH.

Mamatkulova Maftuna Khikmatilloevna

Fergana State University English language and literature faculty Foreign
language and literature: english

Abstract. This article dwells in detail on the term phraseology and provides information about their degree of intensification. Also, the article examines the specific features of phraseological units in the English language, their comparative analysis in both languages is carried out, and the functional-pragmatic aspect of phraseology is studied.

Key words: Phraseology, phraseologism, stable (stable) combination, etymology, semantics, phraseography, aphorism (wise words), idiom, proverb, metal.

Along with all world languages, the English language and the place of phraseological units in its composition are incomparable. In other words, phraseology, as an integral part of any language and a unique treasure, has an incomparable contribution to the formation of the language. We found it necessary to comment on the term phraseology in order to make our thoughts clear and understandable on the basis of evidence. Phraseology is the science of complex language units with a stable character from the Greek phrasa - expression, logos - education. Longman presents: "the way that words and phrases are used in a language", (LDOCE, 2009), that is, it can be understood that phrases and lexemes form a certain part of the language and are used together. The formation and composition of phraseological units is one of the main factors that cause many discussions and debates by linguists. In particular, according to the opinion of the linguist scientist B. Yoldoshev: "Phraseological combinations mainly consist of a combination of words, in other words, phraseological units are a separate unit of the language, and according to their structure, they are equal to a free connection or a sentence" (Yo'ldoshev, 1992). Among the views and researches regarding the appearance of phraseological units and their significant impact on the development of the English language, it was taken as the most acceptable option, which began to develop as a scientific language unit in the 20th century (Knappe & Gabriele, 2004). To date, this topic is studied by many linguists. A number of researches are being carried out in terms of relevance, characteristics and uniqueness of this language unit. This article presents some information about the lexical-semantic composition, characteristics and diversity of phraseological units in the language. Linguist Professor Kunin says: "Phraseological units are a group of words whose meaning changes partially or completely" (Kunin, 1996). As can be seen from the above considerations,

some phraseological units are used with the translation of the lexemes in their composition preserved, and others with a completely changed translation.

A stable language unit consisting of two or more components, meaning a single phraseological meaning, is called a phraseologism or a phraseological combination (phrase). But if we want to give it a broader definition, phraseology comes into the speech ready in advance, and its most important feature is to differentiate and distinguish phraseologisms from word combinations that are formed in speech (that is, not ready in advance), and on this basis, to determine the signs of phraseologisms. Many researchers understand phraseology in a broad sense, depending on the specific differences between idiom-phraseologisms, phraseological compounds and stable sentences: proverbs and proverbs, other phraseological equivalents, stable compounds frozen in human language. When it is understood in a broad sense, the scope of phraseology includes proverbs and proverbs, stable sentences characteristic of folklore, and some forms of communication (greetings, farewell sentences) that have become frozen in our language.

Usually, phraseological units whose meaning has partially changed are rare in English. "Kick the bucket" is literally translated as "kick the bucket". In fact, it is used as a phraseological unit meaning "to turn a blind eye to life", i.e. to die. The words "kick", "the", "bucket" in this unit completely lose their meaning and create a new meaning. It is this situation that increases the attractiveness of the language and the speech expressed in this language. In addition, the lexemes in this combination can be the basis for further enrichment of the language vocabulary, creating a new meaning. In most cases, there is a combination that is common in round interviews and oral exams. This phraseological unit is considered to have a negative connotation and is found not only on the streets, but also in literary sources. "Don't beat the bush" can be translated as "don't beat the bush" when translated directly, but it is exactly the meaning that the English intended, it is translated as "don't run away empty-handed" and in such situations is used. Instead of saying what was said, this combination is used when saying something unrelated to the topic.

Below is an example of a phraseological combination (a phraseological combination is a combination that has a partially figurative meaning, has a semantic motivation, and its components can be easily separated from the syntactic point of view. The components of such combinations can also be replaced by synonyms). The phraseological combination fix (stop, clean) smb's clock, when translated literally into Uzbek, gives a phrase that is morally insane in our language, such as "to fix (stop) someone's clock". However, there are enough expressions in the Uzbek language that

correspond to it. One of them is "to straighten someone's hair". "We'll clean the Dodgers' clocks today." We'll be rooting for the Dodgers today. Or: Let's pay attention to the example in Uzbek language. There is an administrator, Oljaboy's hair needs to be straightened.

If we look carefully, in the examples in both languages, the meanings such as to kill someone, to silence someone, to give away the influence are understood, but if we replace these phraseological combinations with one of the above synonyms, the artistic color of the word may be lost and the level of amplification (intensification) in speech may decrease. Let's compare: We're going to cover the Dodgers today. There is an administrator, Oljaboy's voice should be silenced. Also, if we analyze the phrase to give smb a pain in the neck, although the literal translation corresponds to the phrase "to give smb a pain in the neck", in fact, it corresponds to such combinations as "to play on someone's nerves, to touch someone's soul", and the most suitable equivalent in Uzbek is probably "to be salty on the forehead". There were times when Joe could be a real pain in the neck. Once upon a time, Joey was a scumbag.

So, in most phraseological combinations, word construction and meaning are partially connected, but in some, it can be observed that they are fundamentally different. This shows the vocabulary of the language. According to Abdug'aniyeva: "Phraseological units express the originality, uniqueness, lexical richness of the language" (Abdug'aniyev, 2014). Phraseological units are characterized by the stability of the grammatical form of their components. Each member of phraseological units is repeated in a certain grammatical form that cannot be changed arbitrarily. For example: let's take the combination "ups and downs". This combination is translated as "achievements and shortcomings". If the suffix "s", which forms the plural form of nouns in English, is omitted in this combination, the meaning changes completely. "up and down" is translated from one side to the other and represents the development of the situation. The word home in the combination "take-home pay", which means "net salary", cannot be used in place of its alternatives - house, apartment, dwelling, or the word take, such as get, reach, because these combinations, Shakespeare's era There are many adopted compounds in the literature, and until now, the knot is used in an unchanging state.

In conclusion, it can be said that these units are the most attractive integral part of the language in both written and spoken forms. It can be seen that the contribution of phraseological units to the enrichment and further development of the language is huge.

References:

1. Mayor, M. (2009) "The Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English", Pearson Education Limited, fifth edition.
2. Y'oldoshev.B, "Literary language norm of phraseologisms", T...O'TA, 1992, No.
3. Knappe, Gabriele, "Idioms and fixed expressions in English language study", 2004
4. Kunin A.V, "The modern English phraseology", "book for foreign languages", 1996
5. Webster.M, "Dicitionary and thesaurus", revised and updated edition, "Quad Graphics" printing, Massachusetts, ISBN 978-0-87779-863-7, 2014

